

Deposition of Vanadium Oxide (VO_x) Thin Films by DC and RF Magnetron Sputtering.

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Abstract:

Vanadium oxides represent an important class of materials with high potential in many technological applications based on their diverse temperature-dependent electronic properties. There are large variety of the vanadium oxide phases such as VO, V₂O₃, VO₂, V₂O₅ etc. Depending on the ambient conditions and temperature, phase transformations between these oxides can occur. In addition, several vanadium oxides undergo metal-to-insulator transitions (MIT), e.g., V₂O₃ at ~150 K, VO₂ at ~340 K (67 °C). These complex structural and electronic transformations may play a crucial role in the behavior of vanadium-based systems. Among all, VO₂ has smaller absorption in the far IR wavelength of 8–12 μm and it shows a large temperature coefficient of resistance. VO_x thin films were deposited on Si₃N₄/Si(100) substrate by using DC and RF sputtering. The depositions of VO_x thin films were carried out by varying substrate temperature, plasma power, Ar/O₂ ratio and working pressure. The structural characterization of the films was carried out by using XRD and AFM. The transition temperature of the grown VO₂ thin films was found to be around 65 °C.

Keywords: Vanadium oxide, Sputtering, XRD, AFM